

**CANDLE BURNING AT BOTH SIDES: LIVED EXPERIENCES OF OPERATING ROOM
(OR) NURSES IN COPING WITH BURNOUT AND BUILDING RESILIENCE**

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Abstract

Burnout among OR nurses significantly affect their well-being and patient care. This study explored the experiences of ten OR nurses at Ilocos Training and Regional Medical Center from February to March 2025, using a descriptive phenomenological design. Findings revealed that burnout stemmed from emotional and physical exhaustion due to long hours, cognitive overload, and patient suffering, leading to fatigue, detachment, and decreased motivation. The high-pressure nature of surgical procedures and unpredictable emergencies further intensified stress. Despite these challenges, OR nurses employed coping mechanisms such as mindfulness, exercise, peer support, humor, and reflective practices to build resilience. A supportive work environment and shared experiences with colleagues played a crucial role in alleviating emotional fatigue and sustaining commitment. Humor and positive reframing were commonly used to manage stress and maintain morale. The study emphasized the need for sustainable organizational interventions, including flexible schedules, rest periods, and ergonomic support, to mitigate burnout. Wellness programs incorporating mindfulness training, physical fitness, and peer support were recommended to improve job satisfaction and patient safety. Structured debriefings and reflective practices, such as post-surgery discussions, reinforced the meaningful impact of nurses' work. Based on these findings, the study proposed a Comprehensive Wellness Program to enhance OR nurses' well-being, retention, and long-term resilience.

Keywords: Burnout, resilience, coping mechanisms, wellness programs, operating room nurses, job satisfaction

Introduction

The operating room (OR) is one of the most intense and high-stakes environments in healthcare, requiring nurses to work with precision, focus, and quick decision-making. Their responsibilities go beyond assisting in surgical procedures; they must ensure a sterile field, prepare instruments, monitor patient stability, and collaborate effectively with the surgical team. The unpredictable nature of surgeries, coupled with the pressure to maintain patient safety, makes the OR a particularly stressful workplace. This constant exposure to high-pressure situations puts OR nurses at significant risk for burnout and emotional fatigue.

Burnout is a critical issue in the nursing profession, especially among OR nurses who experience chronic stress and physical exhaustion. According to Kusumawati et al. (2024), burnout is a psychological syndrome characterized by emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and a reduced sense of personal accomplishment. This phenomenon is particularly prevalent in high-stress healthcare settings, where constant exposure to emergencies and long working hours can take a toll on nurses' well-being. Long working hours, rotating shifts, and the emotional toll of handling life-and-death situations contribute to the development of burnout. If left unaddressed, burnout can lead to absenteeism, decreased job satisfaction, and even the decision to leave the profession entirely (Chiu et al., 2024; Tang et al., 2024).

Several studies have highlighted the impact of burnout among OR nurses which emphasized its consequences on both healthcare professionals and patient outcomes. A study by Abou Hashish et al. (2024) found that OR nurses experience higher levels of burnout compared to those in other nursing specialties due to prolonged exposure to critical situations and the pressure to maintain efficiency. Also, research by Sibuea et al. (2024) identified a strong correlation between burnout and increased absenteeism, reduced job satisfaction, and higher turnover rates in OR nursing. The demanding work environment, lack of adequate rest, and emotional burden of handling complex surgical procedures contribute significantly to these challenges.

Furthermore, adequate staffing and workload management are critical in preventing burnout among OR nurses. When hospitals face staffing shortages, nurses are often required to work extended hours, leading to increased fatigue and decreased efficiency. Ensuring that nurse-to-patient ratios are appropriate and that work schedules allow for sufficient rest can significantly reduce stress levels. Workplace interventions also play a crucial role in preventing burnout and fostering resilience among OR nurses. Support systems such as counseling programs, mental health workshops, and structured debriefing sessions help nurses process traumatic experiences and manage emotional stress. Hospital policies that promote reasonable work schedules, sufficient rest periods, and staff recognition initiatives contribute to a more sustainable work environment. When nurses feel valued and supported, they are more likely to remain engaged and motivated in their roles, ultimately improving both their well-being and the quality of patient care.

In the context of the Philippines, a study by Remegio et al. (2021) examined the burnout levels of nurses in surgical settings across several hospitals in Metro Manila. The study identified high workload, emotional strain, and insufficient support from colleagues and management as primary contributors to burnout among Filipino OR nurses. The findings aligned with international studies, indicating that nurses in the Philippines face similar challenges in managing work-related stress.

On the other hand, this research study is significant in many fronts. It explores the experiences of operating room nurses in relation to two critical issues in nursing - resilience and burnout. Resilience is an important quality for nurses as they face numerous challenges in their work, such as high workload, long hours, and exposure to stressful situations. Understanding how operating room nurses at the ITRMC experience and manage resilience, the study can provide

insights into how nurses can be better supported to maintain their resilience and continue to provide high-quality care to patients.

The study was conducted at the Ilocos Training and Regional Medical Center (ITRMC), a tertiary government hospital in San Fernando City, La Union, which serves as a critical healthcare hub for patients across Region I and neighboring provinces. As a referral center for complex surgical cases, ITRMC's Operating Room (OR) Department is characterized by high patient turnover, long operating hours, and intense procedural demands, placing considerable physical and emotional stress on its nursing workforce. OR nurses in this setting frequently endure extended shifts, unpredictable schedules, and emotionally charged environments, leading to chronic fatigue and heightened vulnerability to burnout. Despite these challenges, formal wellness interventions tailored to their needs remain limited. Given this context, there is a compelling need to explore the lived experiences of OR nurses at ITRMC to understand how they cope with stress and build resilience. The findings of this study will provide a foundational basis for creating evidence-informed wellness programs that are responsive to the unique pressures of perioperative nursing in high-demand hospital settings like ITRMC.

Also, the study provides a platform for the voices of operating room nurses to be heard and their experiences to be documented. Giving them an opportunity to share their lived experiences, the study can provide a better understanding of the challenges and opportunities faced by operating room nurses in the context of the ITRMC. Overall, the study can have significant implications for the nursing profession, as it can inform the development of interventions and support programs that enhance resilience, prevent burnout, and improve the overall work environment for operating room nurses.

Statement of the Objectives

The study explored and described the lived experiences of operating room nurses at the Ilocos Training and Regional Medical Center in coping with burnout and building resilience.

Methodology

Research Design. The study employed a descriptive phenomenology approach, a qualitative method that focused on exploring lived experiences by examining participants' perceptions and meanings (Boswell & Cannon, 2020). This approach was utilized to gain a deep understanding of burnout and resilience among OR nurses at Ilocos Training and Regional Medical Center (ITRMC) from February to March 2025. The study followed a phenomenological reflective lifeworld approach, emphasizing the participants' firsthand accounts and subjective realities as essential data sources for uncovering the essence of their experiences.

Participants and Locale of the Study. The study was conducted at the Ilocos Training and Regional Medical Center (ITRMC) from February to March 2025 and included OR nurses with at least five years of experience. Using purposive sampling, ten participants were selected, achieving data saturation with the tenth participant. This sampling method ensured that the study captured a diverse range of experiences while focusing on those with extensive OR nursing backgrounds. Non-OR nurses and those with less than five years of OR experience were excluded to maintain the study's focus on experienced practitioners.

Data Gathering Tools. The data were collected through audio-recorded, semi-structured interviews conducted over the phone, via video chat, or in person, depending on the participants' preferences. This flexible approach allowed nurses to share their experiences in a comfortable and familiar setting, encouraging more open and reflective responses. The semi-structured nature of the interviews provided a framework for exploring the key themes of burnout and resilience while allowing participants the freedom to elaborate on their personal narratives.

Data Analysis. Thematic analysis, a widely used method in qualitative research, involves identifying and reporting patterns and themes within qualitative data (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). This study employed this approach to analyze the data collected from operating room nurses. The process began with familiarization, where researchers reviewed interview transcripts and field notes to gain a comprehensive understanding of the data. This initial step involved reading and re-reading the data to capture its overall meaning. Following this, the researchers generated initial codes by identifying and labeling relevant data segments, a critical step in organizing the information into meaningful categories. These codes were then organized into broader, more abstract themes that captured recurring patterns or concepts within the data (Dunning et al., 2024). Researchers either used an inductive approach, allowing themes to emerge naturally from the data, or a deductive approach, guided by pre-existing theories. Once the initial themes were established, they were carefully reviewed and refined to ensure their relevance and alignment with the coded data. This stage included assessing whether the themes accurately captured the participants' experiences and adjusting as necessary. The final step involved defining and naming the themes, providing detailed descriptions supported by data excerpts to clearly convey the key findings.

Results

Theme 1: Emotional and Physical Exhaustion. The first major theme identified from the narratives of operating room (OR) nurses was emotional and physical exhaustion, reflecting the intense demands of their roles. This exhaustion stemmed from long hours of standing, performing repetitive tasks, and the high-stakes nature of patient care during surgeries. Nurses often experienced significant physical strain, including muscle fatigue from prolonged standing and the repetitive nature of tasks like instrument handling and patient positioning. Emotionally, these nurses faced the psychological toll of managing patient suffering, dealing with critical situations, and maintaining constant vigilance, which led to feelings of detachment, reduced motivation, and chronic fatigue. Four key subthemes emerged under this major theme: (1) Extended Work Hours and Shift Fatigue, highlighting the cumulative physical and mental fatigue from long shifts; (2) High Physical Demands and Repetitive Tasks, focusing on the physical toll of static postures and continuous precision work; (3) Cognitive Overload and Mental Fatigue, capturing the stress of multitasking and rapid decision-making under pressure; and (4) Exposure to Patient Suffering and Trauma, reflecting the emotional burden of witnessing severe patient distress and adverse outcomes.

Theme 2: Stress Triggers in the Operating Room Environment. The second major theme identified from the narratives of operating room (OR) nurses was stress triggers in the OR environment, highlighting the intense pressures that contribute to burnout. The fast-paced, high-stakes nature of the OR presents numerous stressors, including the urgency of surgical procedures, high patient turnover, and the unpredictable nature of medical complications. These factors require nurses to maintain precision and composure under significant time constraints, leading to physical and emotional strain. Three critical subthemes emerged under this major theme: Time Pressure and Urgency of Surgical Procedures, which captures the constant demand for quick, accurate actions in life-saving situations; High Patient Turnover and Heavy Workload, reflecting the challenges of managing multiple critical cases with minimal recovery time; and Unpredictable Surgical Complications, emphasizing the stress caused by sudden, unexpected medical crises that require immediate, decisive responses.

Theme 3: Effective Coping Mechanisms and Resilience-Building Techniques. The third major theme identified from the narratives of operating room (OR) nurses was effective coping mechanisms and resilience-building techniques, highlighting the strategies these nurses use to manage stress and prevent burnout. These approaches include mindfulness practices, physical exercise, peer support, and humor, all of which help nurses cope with the physical and emotional demands of their work. Mindfulness and meditation practices, for instance, allow nurses to reset mentally and remain present during high-stress situations, reducing anxiety and enhancing focus. Physical exercise, such as jogging, yoga, or gym workouts, provides an outlet for physical and emotional release, helping nurses maintain physical stamina and mental clarity. Peer support and team debriefing are also crucial, as they provide emotional validation and collective coping through shared experiences. Additionally, humor and light-hearted interactions during

routine procedures or post-shift gatherings offer brief moments of relief, fostering positive team dynamics and reducing emotional carryover into personal life.

Theme 4: Role of Personal Values and Professional Identity. The fourth major theme identified from the narratives of operating room (OR) nurses was the role of personal values and professional identity in fostering resilience and preventing burnout. Nurses in this study emphasized the importance of their commitment to patient safety, a deep sense of duty, intrinsic motivation, ethical integrity, and the ability to find meaning in their work. These personal and professional values serve as powerful internal drivers, motivating nurses to persevere even in the face of chronic stress and emotional fatigue. The subthemes identified include Commitment to Patient Safety and Quality Care, which highlights the nurse's unwavering dedication to ensuring optimal patient outcomes; Sense of Duty and Responsibility, reflecting the deep-rooted belief in their critical role as caregivers; Intrinsic Motivation and Passion for Nursing, emphasizing the personal satisfaction derived from helping others; Ethical Integrity and Professional Standards, which reinforce their resolve to provide safe, compassionate care; and Finding Purpose and Meaning in Patient Outcomes, illustrating how positive patient outcomes provide emotional fulfillment and a sense of purpose.

Discussion

Theme 1: Emotional and Physical Exhaustion. Emotional and physical exhaustion emerged as a significant challenge for operating room (OR) nurses, reflecting the intense physical and psychological demands of their roles. Prolonged standing, repetitive movements, and the high-stakes nature of surgical procedures contribute to significant physical strain, leading to muscle fatigue and chronic pain (McIntyre et al., 2024). This is consistent with findings from Kim et al. (2022), who reported that the physical demands of OR nursing, including the need to maintain sterile fields and handle heavy instruments, significantly increase the risk of musculoskeletal disorders. Additionally, the mental toll of constant vigilance, multitasking, and rapid decision-making contributes to cognitive overload and emotional exhaustion, further compounding the physical strain (J. E. Lee et al., 2024). Nurses must remain alert for extended periods, managing critical situations and responding quickly to changing patient conditions, which can lead to reduced motivation and chronic fatigue over time.

The psychological impact of OR nursing extends beyond physical strain, encompassing emotional challenges associated with patient suffering and trauma exposure. Witnessing severe patient distress, managing life-threatening complications, and dealing with adverse surgical outcomes can lead to compassion fatigue and emotional burnout (Lex et al., 2024). These findings align with studies Ekingen et al. (2023), which suggest that repeated exposure to traumatic events can erode nurses' emotional resilience, increasing their risk of burnout and reducing job satisfaction. To address this, healthcare organizations must prioritize interventions that reduce physical strain, provide psychological support, and promote mental resilience, such as mindfulness training and regular recovery breaks (Mehra et al., 2024). Implementing supportive work environments and promoting self-care practices are critical steps in reducing the emotional and physical toll on OR nurses, ultimately improving both nurse well-being and patient care outcomes.

Theme 2: Stress Triggers in the Operating Room Environment. Stress triggers in the OR environment are another critical factor contributing to nurse burnout, as highlighted by the narratives in this study. Time pressure and the urgency of surgical procedures often require nurses to make rapid, high-stakes decisions, creating a high-stress environment that can compromise both mental and physical health (Park et al., 2023). For instance, the need to act quickly in life-threatening situations can increase cognitive load, leading to mental fatigue and reduced decision-making capacity (Olasupo, 2023). This aligns with research by Jones et al. (2024), which found that healthcare professionals working in fast-paced settings are more likely to experience cognitive overload and emotional exhaustion due to the constant pressure to perform flawlessly under time constraints.

Additionally, high patient turnover and unpredictable surgical complications further exacerbate stress levels among OR nurses. The need to quickly transition between critical cases without adequate recovery time can lead to cumulative fatigue and emotional burnout (Lotfi et al., 2022). This is consistent with findings from Lee et al. (2024), who reported that high patient volumes and frequent task-switching significantly increase the risk of burnout in surgical teams. To mitigate these stressors, healthcare

organizations should implement strategies that promote work-life balance, improve staffing levels, and incorporate regular debriefing sessions to help nurses process challenging experiences and reduce stress (Martín et al., 2024). Investing in supportive workplace cultures that prioritize staff well-being can enhance nurse retention and improve overall patient care outcomes.

Theme 3: Effective Coping Mechanisms and Resilience-Building Techniques. Effective coping mechanisms and resilience-building strategies were identified as crucial factors in helping OR nurses manage the intense pressures of their work environments. Mindfulness practices, physical exercise, and peer support emerged as essential tools for maintaining mental and physical well-being. For example, mindfulness techniques, such as deep breathing and meditation, have been shown to reduce stress and improve focus, allowing nurses to remain present and calm during high-pressure situations (Suzuki et al., 2024). Physical exercise, including activities like yoga and jogging, not only helps nurses maintain physical stamina but also provides emotional relief, reducing the risk of burnout (Lee et al., 2022). These findings align with research by Siahvashi et al. (2024), which suggests that regular physical activity can enhance resilience by promoting endorphin release and reducing stress hormone levels.

Humor and light-hearted interactions also play a critical role in fostering positive team dynamics and reducing emotional carryover into personal life. Informal peer support, such as post-shift debriefing sessions and shared humor, can provide emotional validation and strengthen team cohesion (Riguzzi et al., 2024). This aligns with studies by Hughes et al. (2024), which found that teams with strong social bonds and supportive communication are more resilient to stress and less likely to experience burnout. To maximize the benefits of these coping strategies, healthcare organizations should create environments that encourage open communication, provide access to mental health resources, and promote work-life balance. This holistic approach can help OR nurses maintain long-term emotional well-being and job satisfaction.

Theme 4: Role of Personal Values and Professional Identity. Personal values and professional identity also emerged as critical factors in sustaining motivation and resilience among OR nurses. Nurses who are deeply committed to patient safety and quality care often view their work as a calling, deriving intrinsic motivation from the ability to positively impact patient outcomes (Dermer et al., 2024; Rivaz et al., 2024). This internal drive, coupled with a strong sense of duty and responsibility, helps nurses persevere even in the face of chronic stress and emotional exhaustion (Aberhe et al., 2024). These findings are consistent with research by (Tussing et al., 2024), which highlights the protective effects of intrinsic motivation and professional commitment in reducing burnout and promoting long-term career satisfaction.

Moreover, the ability to find meaning in patient outcomes provides emotional fulfillment, reinforcing nurses' commitment to their roles (Kolutek et al., 2024). For many OR nurses, the satisfaction of helping patients recover and the recognition of their contributions to life-saving procedures provide a powerful sense of purpose, helping them cope with the emotional challenges of their work (Wolff et al., 2024). This aligns with studies by Oldenmenger et al. (2024), which suggest that healthcare professionals who view their work as meaningful are more resilient to burnout and more likely to remain engaged in their roles. To support this, healthcare organizations should foster a culture of appreciation, provide opportunities for professional growth, and promote reflective practices that reinforce nurses' sense of purpose and professional identity (Monterde-Estrada et al., 2024; Parlak et al., 2024; Yehene et al., 2024).

Conclusions

The findings of this study underscore the significant physical and emotional challenges faced by operating room (OR) nurses, highlighting the critical need for comprehensive support systems to mitigate burnout and promote resilience. Emotional and physical exhaustion, stress triggers in the OR environment, effective coping mechanisms, and personal values emerged as central themes, reflecting the multifaceted nature of burnout in this high-stakes profession. While OR nurses face intense physical strain, cognitive overload, and emotional fatigue, they also demonstrate remarkable resilience through mindfulness, physical exercise, peer support, and a deep commitment to patient safety and quality care. These coping strategies, combined with strong personal values and professional identity, provide a resilient foundation that enables nurses to navigate their demanding roles. To sustain this resilience and improve nurse retention, healthcare

organizations must prioritize interventions that reduce physical strain, promote mental well-being, and reinforce the intrinsic motivations that drive nurses to provide compassionate, high-quality care.

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